

COMPOSITE REPAIR USING THE INTERNET TECHNOLOGY

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ABSTRACT

As composite materials are gaining wide acceptance in aircraft structure, repair of damaged composite is becoming an important issue. The issues in composite repair include high cost, material interchangeability, water ingress, and structural integrity. To address these problems, researchers have studied on the composite repair in various aspects.

In this paper, an Internet-based advisory service (called Repair Advisory Service, RAS) for composite repair is proposed to increase efficiency for repair process. In the RAS system the web browser is used as its user interface, which provides easy access to the service. The RAS server provides web-based tools for failure prediction, Structural Repair Manual (SRM), automated prepreg cutting process, material properties, inventory and knowledge base.

The computer codes implemented for repair design estimates the tensile failure and shear failure of repaired structures. The prediction of failure is based on the maximum strain criterion for tensile failure while elastic-perfect plastic shear failure model is applied for interfacial failure. The OEM's SRM is provided in the PDF format for viewing and searching by web browsers instead of looking up paper version SRM. The knowledge base in this site offers a room to share and distribute ideas, memos, publications, or suggestions from the repair engineers. The fabrication tool of RAS reads repair geometry from engineers then generates a CNC toolpath to cut prepreg patches.

The RAS service is open to public and available at <http://nano.gsnu.ac.kr/>. Broad feedback from field technicians and engineers is welcome to improve the usefulness of RAS.

KEYWORDS : Composite, Repair, Internet, Automation, NC code

INTRODUCTION□

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As composite materials are gaining wide acceptance in aircraft structures, repair of damaged composite is becoming an important issue. The issues in composite repair include high cost, material interchangeability, low temperature-curable repair prepreg, water ingress, and structural integrity. To address these problems, an international committee called Commercial Aircraft Composite Repair Committee (CACRC) was formed with the objective to develop standards on composite repair [1]. Although a number of researchers have studied on repair techniques, mechanical properties, and mathematical modeling [2-13], a large portion of the previous work was focused on manual repair that inherently requires labor-intensive fabrication process.

In this paper, an Internet-based advisory service for composite repair is proposed to assist repair engineers and technicians with computerized design and fabrication tools.

REPAIR PROCESS□

A typical repair process starts from the identification of damage. Once the type of original material, in other words base material, and size of the damaged area are identified, field technicians either consult to repair engineers for further repair processes, or proceed repair without special supervision. Fig. 1 shows scarf and lap repair techniques, which are typical methods of repairing composites. Most small size repair is conducted according to the Structural Repair Manual (SRM) written by the

Original Equipment Manufacturers (OEM) of aircrafts [14, 15]. For large damage, engineers' decision on the repair process is required. If the damage is too severe and large to handle in the airline's repair station, the damaged component ought to be shipped to the OEM for advanced repair. Although repair materials and techniques have been advanced, field repair still involves manual processes such as SRM look-up, fabric cutting, hand lay-up, and heat-blanket curing. Thus, the quality of repaired part depends somewhat upon craftsmanship of repair technicians.

Fig. 1. Scarf and lap repair.

REPAIR ADVISORY SERVICE (RAS)

RAS has been developed for composite repair taking advantage of the Internet technology. As a communication tool, the Internet provides advantages in composite repair: a) easy and fast access to repair related information and b) tight connection between design and fabrication of repair resulting in reduced repair time.

1. Communication of RAS

In order to share information effectively throughout the network, the 3-tier client-server architecture is applied to the RAS system (Fig. 2). Having web browsers as its user interface (1st tier), accessibility to the service is maximized. Thus, engineers and technicians in different repair stations can access the RAS server (2nd tier) via the web browser to obtain information that is located in several modules (3rd tier). At the time of writing, the test version of RAS is open to public via the Internet, but its communication system can be modified and customized for a specific airliner depending on their network environment.

Fig. 2. Schematic communication model of RAS.

2. Components of RAS

The components in RAS are shown in Fig. 3, which have the functionality as follows:

- Failure Load Design
The failure load and mode of lap repair and scarf repair are calculated by computer codes. The

computer codes predict tensile failure and shear failure of repaired structure. The prediction of tensile failure is based on the maximum strain criterion for tensile failure while the elastic-perfect plastic shear failure model is applied for interfacial failure [3]. The shear failure model was modified from the Hart-Smith model [16] to accommodate the Anisotropic property of individual composite layer.

Fig. 3 shows the web-based user interfaces for failure load design of the scarf repair and lap repair. The web pages read geometric parameters of each repair type, laminate stacking sequence of laminate, and environment conditions such as dry/room-temperature or hot/wet.

(a) Scarf Repair

(b) Lap repair

Fig. 3. Web-based user interfaces of RAS.

Once a user designs the parameters for a repair and submit the results, the parameters are transmitted to RAS server via the Internet. A numerical solution for the given repaired structure is obtained, and the results are shown to the user as another web page (Fig. 4). Based on the failure load results, engineers can evaluate the load carrying capacity of various repair designs.

(a) Scarf Repair

(b) Lap repair

Fig. 4. Failure prediction results from RAS.

- Web-based SRM

The OEMs' SRM is provided in the PDF format for viewing and searching by web browsers instead of looking up paper version manuals (Fig. 5). If faster and easier search for specific information is desired, the format of SRM may be revised to enable more graphical navigation.

- Fabrication

For the repair procedure of cutting lay-up into the designed dimensions, automated cutter provides higher efficiency than manual process. As shown in Fig. 6, the web-based RAS interface reads dimensions required for scarf repair. Currently concentric circular cutting pattern is available in RAS for testing purpose. RAS generates G&M codes promptly that the engineer can upload the code to the cutter. Among different types of commercial ply cutting machines, 3-axis CNC cutter is used. The machine control language used in RAS is G&M code, which is standard code for CNC cutters.

Fig. 5. An example of web-based SRM.

Fig. 6. User interface for automated fabrication.

Fig. 7 shows an example of G&M code generated by the fabrication module of RAS. The RAS server can accommodate other hardware language besides G&M code by modified toolpath planner. The repair prepreg is automatically tailored into a series of circular laminate patches (Fig. 8). It makes easy for repair engineers just to layout the patches into the damaged area in proper order.

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- Knowledge Base
 Although standard processes of repair is well documented, practical knowledge from field technicians and engineers is valuable to share. The knowledge-base in RAS is a small database to acquire and distribute ideas, memos, publications, or suggestions from the field engineers.
- Search Engine
 Google's [17] search engine is embedded in the site to look up requested key words in the entire documents linked to the RAS website.

SCENARIO

After damage inspection process (Fig. 9a), a repair engineer accesses to the RAS website from his/her computer (Fig. 9b). Using RAS, the repair engineer can search and view relevant documents for specific part to be repaired. If necessary the load carrying capacity of the repaired composite can be estimated in a few seconds in the RAS server (Fig. 9c). Once the engineer makes decision on repair, he/she removes the damaged area by router and other mechanical tools (Fig. 9e). While the process of material removal is in progress, the repair prepreg can be cut by automated cutting machine according to patch geometry. The engineer can apply the repair patches and vacuum bagging layers to the cleansed surface of the damaged part. While heating up the heat blanket to cure composite, the engineer can start another repair queued on his/her list. Using RAS, the process of composite repair can be expedited by providing web-based automation of prepreg cutting process. The overall result is reduced time and cost of composite repair (Fig. 9e).

Fig. 9. The expedited repair process using the RAS system.

DISCUSSIONS

RAS is a newly proposed software tool and process. Considering practical application of RAS in commercial airliners the following issues are to be discussed.

- Prepreg vs. Wet lay-up: although prepreg for repair purpose such as Hexcel' M20 is developed, wet lay-up is still popular repair process. Prepreg is ready to cut by ply cutter while wet lay-up requires impregnation process before cutting. Since the impregnated dry fabric could be relatively difficult to cut, application of automated cutting could be challenging.
- Cost of machine: CNC-based ply cutter is commercially available at low price. For small repair station or for small size airliner, even the cost of cutting machine may be not trivial. The benefit from automated repair is to be compared with manual repair. The number of repair completed in the repair station and time saved by the automated cutting system are the parameters to be considered.
- Authorization: Some repair stations do not have certified engineers to design repair geometry, but merely follow OEM's SRM. In this case, designing or modifying repair geometry that is different from SRM cannot get authorized.

Emphasizing the bright side of the web-based information exchange, however, RAS has following advantages over current practice of composite repair.

- Searching information via web is gaining more ground than looking up thick paper version documents. With structured SRM and other in-house documents available in web can increase efficiency of the repair process.
- In addition, knowledge acquired from engineers' experience is a valuable asset for any business organization, especially for a manufacturing company [18]. Web is such an effective tool to store and share the knowledge-base of manufacturing process, here repairing of composite. Memos, tips, industrial news, and process knowledge stored in RAS is possibly reformulated into a knowledge map that can be useful in training of newly hired engineers as well as to provide experienced engineers with check points of standard repair process.

CONCLUSIONS

The web-based RAS has been developed to provide software tools that might be useful in composite repair. The main objective of RAS is to provide process knowledge as well as to encourage and demonstrate an automated repair process. Since it is developed to prove the concept, RAS is open to public and available at <http://nano.gsnu.ac.kr/>. A couple of components in RAS are under development and more repair materials will be included in the database. Broad feedback from field technicians and engineers as well as researchers working on composite repair can improve the usefulness of RAS.

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